

Sadigov A.

*PhD student at Khazar University***Abstract**

The future of Europe had become uncertain after World War II. The eastern part of the continent was liberated from German occupation by the Soviet Red Army, while the western part was liberated from German occupation by the American-British alliance. The conflict between the US and the USSR, who were allies throughout the war, that began with the First Berlin Crisis would give way to the period known as the Cold War. During the 1948-1956 period, the Soviet government would set out to establish various socialist and Soviet satellite regimes in Eastern Europe. One result of this was the emergence of opposition movements in Eastern Europe. These movements, which increased after Stalin's death in 1953, would change form after 1956 and continue in their new form until the end of the Cold War.

Keywords: Cold War, Eastern Europe, USSR, Opposition, Socialism in Many Countries.

Europe had experienced great devastation during World War II, and after the war, great uncertainties had left the future of the continent and the wars unknown. The eastern part of the continent was liberated from occupation by the Soviet Red Army, while the western part was liberated from occupation by the United States (US)-British (and nominally French) allied forces. While the future of Europe was determined by American aid and policies on the one hand, Soviet aid and policies on the other hand would be influential.

Within this framework, the future of Eastern Europe, that is, the region liberated from Nazi occupation by Soviet Red Army units, would be shaped by international balances on the one hand, and Soviet leader Stalin's choices on the other. Two important problems in this region were whether the decisions of the Soviet leadership would coincide with the decisions of the Soviets' Western allies, and whether a conflict between the demands of the local population and Soviet interests would be satisfactory in its solution.

In this article, an attempt will be made to read the situation by reviewing the experience of Eastern Europe from the very end of the Second World War until the Hungarian Revolution, taking into account the changes that occurred after Stalin's death.

EUROPE AFTER WORLD WAR II

Eastern Europe, in addition to experiencing significant changes in World War I, was also struggling with a balancing policy in the interwar period to adjust its relations with the more established states of Europe. World War II emerged on the stage of history as a period that changed the existing balances and reshaped the fate of Eastern Europe. During World War II, resistance forces with different ideological concerns emerged in the Eastern European countries occupied by Nazi Germany, and while Yugoslavia and Albania liberated themselves and chose socialism, Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, Czechoslovakia, Poland and the parts of Germany east of the Elbe River were liberated from Nazi occupation by the armies of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), but in line with Soviet leader Stalin's post-war predictions, pro-Soviet regimes were established in these countries.(1)

The negotiations and planning for the post-war period had already taken place while World War II was still ongoing. During the planning phase, US President Franklin Delano Roosevelt and USSR President Joseph

Stalin had different visions for the post-World War II period. Roosevelt saw the disappearance of global economic integration and the lack of an organization where the great powers could negotiate through diplomacy as the cause of the war (the League of Nations, which existed at the time, was extremely unsuccessful in this regard) and envisioned organizations that would provide economic and diplomatic integration for the post-war period. In fact, institutions such as the United Nations, the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank Group, and the World Trade Organization, which were established after the war, were the results of this mindset.

Although Roosevelt died before seeing the end of the war, his ideas would continue to this day by becoming institutions. On the other hand, Stalin was thinking of a system in which only the USSR and specifically Russia would not suffer similar damage after the war. Indeed, the Soviets had lost around 27 million² citizens in the war and according to Stalin, this situation should never happen again. Stalin found the solution to this issue in creating a buffer zone between them and Germany, which was thought to be the common cause of World War III. The practical version of this situation was the idea of "simultaneous Socialism in many countries", which caused him to enter into serious competition with Trotsky at the time and led to Trotsky's exile from the USSR. Therefore, the Soviets' perspective on the post-war period was more pragmatic than Roosevelt's USA and was based on exporting Socialism to the lands they had liberated from Nazi occupation in Eastern Europe in order to create a buffer zone so that the USSR would not be directly attacked again. Stalin now put aside the idea of "Socialism in One Country", which he believed in and was the main point of contention between him and Trotsky, for geostrategic reasons and defended the idea of "Socialism in Many Countries".(3)

The idea of Socialism in One Country argued that the Socialist Revolution should mature only in the USSR and transform into Communism, that when socialism reached its desired state, the country would export its ideology to the world and that the entire world would become communist by this method but in the long term, and therefore there was no need to use resources to export Socialism to the rest of the world. The idea of (Simultaneous) Socialism in Many Countries,

which Trotsky also advocated and was considered a more universal idea, imagined that socialism should be exported from the Soviet Union to the industrially developed countries of the world simultaneously or in the near future and that this should be achieved by strengthening the socialist formations in these countries, and that since the important countries in the world would thus become Socialist, a joint effort should be made to reach Communism.⁴ Stalin's decision while the war was ongoing was to ensure that as many Socialist regimes as possible were established in Europe, in the west of the USSR.

The different scenarios that the American and Soviet sides created for the post-war period were of course reflected in the field and diplomatic relations during the final stages of the war. The competition over who would liberate the lands occupied by Nazi Germany (the so-called Third German Reich) was based on Roosevelt and Stalin's different future predictions. This competition, which began between the American-British forces and the Soviet Red Army after the Normandy Landing in 1944, as the end of the war was approaching, was not yet a competition close to the Cold War concept, but it was an extremely important conflict in terms of its results. While the Americans captured Italy and France, the Soviets "liberated" about one-third of Germany's eastern territory, along with Austria, Hungary, Czechoslovakia, Romania, Bulgaria and Poland, as a result of an advance that coincided with the center of Germany in Eastern Europe. Since this situation seemed obvious beforehand, Soviet Union President Joseph Stalin and the British Prime Minister at the time, Sir Winston Churchill, exchanged views on the future of Europe; the two leaders even discussed dividing Eastern Europe and the Balkans into zones of influence of Britain and the USSR on a country basis, first in their joint meetings in Moscow in 1943 and then at the Tehran Conference. When the paper with the decisions was discussed whether to burn it or not, Stalin gave the paper to Churchill, saying, "You keep it."⁽⁴⁾

However, after Adolf Hitler committed suicide on April 30, 1945, the surrender of the Nazi Third Reich on May 2, 1945 began a real division, the European continent was effectively divided into Soviet and American-British control zones, and the Allies divided Germany and Berlin between them on June 5, 1945.⁶ In particular, after the US used atomic bombs twice against Japan on August 6 and 9, 1945, a polarization began and the Churchill-Stalin agreement began to be gradually shelved.

Churchill nevertheless developed a common understanding with Stalin about Poland's post-war territories and persuaded other leaders to accept territory from Germany along the Curzon Line in exchange for Poland's withdrawal from its eastern borders in favor of the Soviets.

THE GERMAN PROBLEM AND THE BEGINNING OF THE COLD WAR

At the end of the war, there was still no tension between the US and the USSR, and the American side considered the Soviets to be a highly successful ally in the war against the Nazis. Indeed, in this relatively peaceful partnership and common victory environment, the Westminster College speech of former British

Prime Minister Winston Churchill and the long, unsigned telegram of the US Embassy in Moscow, George F. Kennan, again blaming the Soviets, were seen as attempts to sabotage this atmosphere of peaceful coexistence and as injustice to the Soviet side.

Sir Winston Churchill was the first leader to see that Stalin would not honor the verbal agreement he had made with him after the war and would turn the zones of influence into a buffer zone under his occupation, and was the first politician to draw attention to Soviet expansionism while the Western Allies still perceived the Soviets as an ally helping them win against the "great enemy" Fascism. In a speech he gave at Westminster College in Fulton, Missouri, USA, on March 5, 1946, Churchill said the following:

"From Stettin on the Baltic to Trieste on the Adriatic, an Iron Curtain has descended across the Continent. Behind the line are all the capitals and ancient states of Central and Eastern Europe. Warsaw, Berlin, Prague, Vienna, Budapest, Belgrade, Bucharest, and Sofia, all these famous cities and the peoples around them, are in what I may call the Soviet zone, and each of them is in some way subject not only to Soviet influence but also to the very high and sometimes increasing control of Moscow. Only Athens—Greece with its immortal victories—is free to determine its fate by elections under British, American, and French supervision. The Polish Government, under Russian influence, is making vast and very wrong raids on Germany, deporting millions of Germans on a grievous and unimaginable scale. The Communist Parties, which are very small in these Eastern European countries, have been raised to a power and strength far beyond their members, and are striving to gain totalitarian control everywhere. Police states thrive in almost all cases, and for the moment, except in Czechoslovakia, there is no real democracy."

Churchill seemed to see Stalin's general plan in explaining his ideas, but no one in the senior US authorities took the former British Prime Minister seriously, and Churchill was even accused of wanting to start a new war or to tarnish the reputation of a reliable ally in order to regain lost prestige and gain press coverage. There was no source at the time to support Churchill's claims, apart from the telegram sent from Moscow in 1946 by the US diplomat and advisor George F. Kennan, known as the "X Telegram" and published a year later as an article entitled "The Sources of Soviet Behavior".

The elections held in Eastern European countries in 1947, which somehow resulted in the victory of the Communist parties⁹, the Truman Doctrine, which included the US guaranteeing Turkey and Greece against the Soviets in 1947, and finally the Berlin Crisis of 1948-1949, led to the Western allies' trust in the Soviets being replaced by a justified suspicion and a sense of self-defense. The Berlin Crisis and the discussions on what to do with Germany would cause the Soviets and their allies to separate into the Eastern and Western Blocks, and the world to enter a new, non-conflict, ideological scale and constant competitive polarization, and the Cold War would begin between these two blocks.⁽⁵⁾

After the defeat and surrender of the Nazis, the situation in Germany posed a problem for the Allies. Berlin had to be watched over by all four Allies because it was the capital, but the city of Berlin was also located well inside the Soviet-occupied East Germany, approximately 130 kilometers east of the West German border. While France argued that Germany should be disarmed just like it was after World War I and should definitely not be allowed to industrialize, the British administration and the US President at the time, Henry Truman, thought that Germany should be made a part of Europe and seen as a part of the general Western civilization, not the loser of the war. In addition to demanding a large war reparations from Germany, USSR Leader Stalin wanted all systems in Germany that the USSR might need, from thermal power plants to spare parts, to be transferred to the Soviets and Germany to be completely under Soviet control and neutralized. The Western Allies rejected this, and US President Truman also refused to give the industrial facilities that the USSR demanded from West Germany as war reparations.

Germany was struggling with huge economic problems and as a result of the decisions taken at the London Conference in March 1948, it was decided that the regions of Germany under the control of the three Western Allies would be united as a single, independent state under a federal government structure and that the three West German occupation zones would be integrated into the American Aid Plan (Marshall Plan) as a single group. These decisions caused a significant problem in Soviet foreign policy. As a continuation of these decisions and in order to prevent the hyperinflation that Germany was experiencing, it was also decided that a new currency, the German Mark, would be put into effect in West Germany and West Berlin, which was under the control of the three Allies, as of January 1, 1949, and that Germany's economic development would be supported.

The USSR's response to these decisions was harsh. First, they tried to intimidate the people of Berlin with regular communist troops and bring the entire city under Soviet control, but when this failed, they turned to a military solution. On June 24, 1948, Soviet tanks and armored units blocked the road and rail links connecting the Western-controlled sectors of Berlin to West Germany with barricades. Since no agreement had been signed beforehand that these roads would never be closed, the Soviets had the right to cut, close, and thus block the supply routes to West Berlin as they wished, since they were in fact under their control in East Germany. The Soviets made it clear that the use of the roads to Berlin by their Western allies for three years would not entitle them to use them.

Taking military action for Berlin and forcing Soviet troops to withdraw from the railways and roads could have caused a new war that the US and Britain had never planned, perhaps World War III. Although the US had the atomic bomb as a trump card, the Soviets had also made significant progress towards developing their own bomb, largely through information sold by Klaus Fuchs, who worked at the Los Alamos Laboratories, and by 1949 the Soviets would have an atomic bomb of their own. Moreover, the effects of using an

atomic bomb in the middle of Europe would have prevented such a war experience. The US, Britain and France agreed that they could not risk war; however, Berlin was too important a city to be left to the Soviets.

The US Army's Berlin Commander, General Lucius D. Clay, and the US Air Forces' European Commander, General Curtis Le May, began researching whether airlift was possible, and eventually the Berlin Air Lift project emerged. The city's Templehof in the American Sector, Gatow in the British Sector, and Tegel in the French Sector, which were not used but were not included in the agreement with the Soviets regarding the sharing of Berlin, began to be transported by plane from Britain, France, West Germany, and the US to Berlin. On June 26, 1948, when the first flights were made, the transportation process was planned to last three weeks. The operation had to last for more than a year as conditions in Berlin worsened, the need increased, and the Soviets did not back down, thinking that the Western Allies would give up anyway. Although the USSR gave up on closing the roads to Berlin on May 11, 1949, the operation continued until September 30, 1949. During the Berlin Airlift, Britain faced economic hardships not seen in the war. Consumables such as cigarettes and bread were rationed in Britain, and 39 British and 31 American pilots lost their lives during the operation, which included British and American pilots as well as Australian, Canadian, New Zealand and South African pilots. France contributed by expanding one of its airports.

The Berlin Airlift Operation and the Berlin Crisis of 1948-1949 caused and/or supported two more important developments: First, the establishment of West Germany as an independent state and the support of its economic development provided decisive support. Secondly, and perhaps more importantly, on April 4, 1949, the Western powers signed the North Atlantic Treaty and established an important military and political solidarity organization called the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). According to Article 5 of the treaty that determined its existence, NATO stipulated that if any of its members were attacked, it would be considered an attack carried out jointly by all members and that all members would respond to the attack jointly with military force. The USA, Belgium, Britain, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Iceland, Canada, Luxembourg, Norway and Portugal were the founding members of NATO and signed the treaty. Türkiye and Greece became NATO members in 1952, and West Germany in 1955, and the organization continued with these fifteen countries until its second expansion in 1999.

The establishment of the Federal Republic of Germany (West Germany) was officially declared on May 23, 1949. The establishment of NATO and the subsequent formation of West Germany as a single state triggered a number of developments on the Soviet side: First, the establishment of the German Democratic Republic was declared on October 7, 1949. Thus, Germany was divided into East and West Germany, and Berlin was officially divided into East and West regions. In addition, as a military response to the establishment and institutionalization of NATO, the Warsaw Treaty Organization, or more commonly known as the

Warsaw Pact, was established on May 1, 1955, in response to the threat posed by a "re-armed" West Germany. The countries that formed the Warsaw Pact were the USSR, the German Democratic Republic (East Germany), Albania, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Poland and Romania. Except for Albania's withdrawal of support for ideological reasons in 1961 and its formal withdrawal in 1968, the Warsaw Pact members continued their membership unchanged until the Warsaw Treaty Organisation was legally dissolved on 1 July 1991, after the 1989 revolutions.¹²

The Berlin Crisis of 1948-49 and the establishment of NATO showed that the division Churchill had indicated in 1946 was now very clear. The Soviet Union and its forced allies in Central and Eastern Europe and the Balkans were now perceived as defenders of another ideological camp and therefore as enemies of the Western way of life. The 1949 Chinese Communist Revolution, led by Mao-Tse-Tung and which caused the US to completely change its Far East policies, signaled the beginning of a bipolar period in international politics; from then on, there were the Western and Eastern (or Capitalist and Socialist or American and Soviet) Blocks and their ideological conflicts would determine global political trends for the next 40 years. NATO thought that a Third World War would start with an attack on West Germany through East Germany and NATO's initial war strategies were geared towards a war that would start on the East-West German border. This understanding was the essence of NATO's "Forward Strategy".

However, the hot war did not begin in Europe, but in Korea, which had been divided into the Communist North and the Capitalist South after World War II. The 1950-1953 Korean War was also a sign that the race for supremacy between two separate blocs in the world had now spread beyond Europe.

THE COLD WAR AND THE TRANSFORMATION OF EASTERN EUROPE

After 1945, the Soviet presence in Eastern Europe and the Balkans was not limited to political guidance. Stalin initially considered using Eastern Europe as a "buffer zone" to prevent a possible attack or to break its power, considering the losses in lives, land and ammunition that the Germans had inflicted on the Soviets during World War II. However, as the outcome of the war began to take shape, he added the idea of a political formation that would impose the Soviet way of life to this idea of military security. It is interesting that around the same time, Western Europe also tried to unite itself on a more federative, more unified platform of inter-state assistance and cooperation with the Schuman Plan and the resulting European Coal and Steel Union of 1951.

The model Stalin had in mind could be seen as a reflection of the Modernization School in the West, where citizens believed in the establishment of a society without property and eventually Communism as Marx had envisioned. A system in which villages were transformed into organized and unified private farms, collective farms, industrialization was supported, settlement in cities and work and education were encouraged, really had very similar resonances to those of the Modernization theorists in the West. Eastern Europe was also a new area where this system was expanded

after the war. One result of modernization in the Soviet system was the desire to create individuals who were called Homo Sovieticus, who believed that people did not need to own property, that in the transition to communism they had to trust the state and the Communist Party, and that people would evolve by following their guidance, and therefore fully embraced the Socialist idea and believed in the ideal of communism. It was thought that a type of people who studied classical music and literature, were open to urbanization and industrialization, and were blindly loyal to the Party would emerge both in the USSR and in the satellite states of Eastern Europe.⁽²⁾

By 1948, all Eastern European countries were under Soviet control. However, this control was not without problems. The Communist Information Bureau COMINFORM, which was established in 1947 and whose mission could be summarized as ensuring unity of ideology, ideas and action among the communist parties in Eastern Europe, appeared to have ceased to function as early as 1949 and would be disbanded in 1956, as it was no longer active. The real ties that held the Eastern Bloc countries together were the "friendship, defense and cooperation" agreements between the USSR and its individual allies. When we look at these agreements in general, we can see that they generally included the following issues: a) mutual defense agreements; b) prohibition of participation in hostile organizations such as NATO; c) mutual respect for each other's sovereignty and promises not to interfere in their internal affairs. However, this last provision did not prevent the USSR from interfering in the internal affairs of its allies - as did the USA in a more indirect sense.¹³ On the other hand, the Yugoslav Federation, which had established a Socialist regime of its own without Soviet influence, was viewed by Stalin with suspicion rather than with pleasure. The reason why an armed conflict did not occur between the USSR and Yugoslavia was not because the countries with Socialist regimes got along well among themselves and that they would eventually form a general federation, but because the possibility of a conflict of unforeseen dimensions between the two countries would create a bad impression - even lead to rebellion - in Stalin's interests and in other countries under Soviet control.⁽⁵⁾

The Soviet intervention first and most clearly took place in military matters. Stalin wanted all of Eastern Europe to undergo a Soviet-style transformation, and for this purpose thousands of Soviet advisors were dispersed throughout the countries of Eastern Europe. The most important group consisted of soldiers. The first group of military advisors dispersed to the countries of the Eastern Bloc in October 1948, and they were initially very limited in number (e.g. 8-9 people in Hungary), and they insisted that their suggestions were only suggestions, and that the military authorities in the countries they went to should still do things their way. However, in early 1949 a new group of advisors, this time not the number of the fingers of one hand but an army of advisors numbering in the thousands, formed the second wave, and this time this new group of advisors took complete control. Simultaneously, the officers in the Eastern European armies were purged and replaced by workers and peasants who had no connection

with the military. These people, who were working as farmers one day, had received important officer ranks in the army the next, and the Soviet advisors could make them do whatever they wanted and sign whatever documents they wanted.

The economy was again used to expand Soviet control. Thousands of “prisoners of war” were sent to work in the Soviet Union, while joint companies were established with the Soviets in basic industries such as transportation and energy, and individual countries were also directed.¹⁵ Once the army and economic institutions came under Soviet control, it became very difficult for countries to make independent decisions. Thus, the Soviets brought a new order to Eastern Europe.

On the other hand, the only country not included in this cycle was Yugoslavia. Yugoslavia, which had fought its own war of liberation from the Nazi occupation and emerged as a socialist federal state under the leadership of its leader Josiph Bros Tito, had achieved its transition to socialism without Soviet support. This created a significant problem for Stalin in post-war Europe, where all communist parties were directed in coordination. From 1948 onwards, relations between Yugoslavia and the USSR began to deteriorate, and finally in 1949 Yugoslavia cut off relations with the USSR and the Eastern Bloc countries. If the Korean War had not broken out in 1950, Stalin had prepared a plan for the Eastern Bloc countries to invade Yugoslavia in 1950, and with the Korean War he was convinced that the West would not quietly accept the occupation.⁽³⁾

Another area where the Soviet model was applied was politics. In the early days when all other parties were not eliminated, the communists began to form patriotic, democratic or national fronts in cooperation with others, allowing voters to vote for a single candidate in elections. Since Stalin envisioned popular participation, participation rates in elections could sometimes reach 99.99%.

FIRST REACTIONS TO THE SOVIETS

In Europe, things were not going as Stalin wanted. In Eastern Europe, the people were gradually beginning to form a semi-organized uprising against Soviet oppression and the lifestyle that was being forced upon them. However, there was no rebellion during Stalin's last year, most of which he spent in bed sick. Stalin's death on March 5, 1953 and his replacement by a junta consisting not of a single leader but of the leaders of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union were the factors that brought the problems to light in Eastern Europe.

After Stalin died, a power struggle started within the Party and as a result, instead of a single leader, Lavrenty Beria, Gyorgy Malenkov, Lazar Kaganovich, Vyacheslav Molotov, Nikolai Bulganin and Nikita Khrushchev began to jointly lead Stalin. The most important name within this junta was Beria, who had also led the Secret Service and the Ministry of Internal Affairs during Stalin's time. However, in time, Communist Party leaders who thought Beria would have them killed began to support first Malenkov and then Khrushchev, and the struggle continued until Khrushchev became the sole leader of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union on September 7, 1953. Within the Eastern Bloc, the declaration of unthinkable levels of

unrest during Stalin's time, marches, uprisings, changes of leadership independent of the Soviets, and even an armed uprising that changed the regime, albeit briefly, as in Hungary in 1956, were all possible because other Eastern Bloc countries saw this power struggle after Stalin as a weakening of Soviet power and influence. At the same time, the promises of support and aid given by the US to Eastern Europe through the “Radio Free Europe and Radio Liberty” broadcasts since the Berlin Crisis were also effective in these uprisings. Although Khrushchev's intervention in the events and the US never providing the aid it promised quickly eliminated this situation, the events between 1953 and 1957 were of vital importance for Eastern Europe.⁽¹⁾

The possibility that some of Moscow's moves were misinterpreted by the people of Eastern Europe during this period was another important factor in the events that took place between 1953 and 1956. First of all, there was the perception of the power struggle within the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU) as a weakness in the administration. This may have led to the rebels viewing the developments that occurred in East Germany in 1953 as Germany's internal affairs, and therefore thinking that there would be no Soviet intervention.

The first major problem within the Eastern Bloc began with the demonstrations of German heavy industry workers in 1953. In order to overcome Soviet demands and prove themselves to Stalin's successors, the President of the German Democratic Republic, Wilhelm Pieck, and the General Secretary of the German Socialist Unity Party, Walter Ulbricht, increased production quotas in the country, extended shifts, and imposed severe sanctions on workers if they did not meet the quota. When the quotas were increased by 10% on June 16, 1953, around 60 construction workers working on the construction of Karl Marx Allée, East Berlin's main street, went on strike, and industrial workers revolted on June 17, and the demonstrations in East Berlin quickly turned into violent riots with 100,000 participants. Soviet soldiers had to intervene in the incident, after the German people's police (Volkspolizei) cornered the demonstrators in a square, Soviet T-34 tanks entered the square and according to official records 51 people died, according to some witnesses 125 (and even according to one reading more than 250).

The action of the German workers was a very important action in terms of the Soviet regime envisioning a system based on working class domination, and for this reason its impact on the world was great.

THE POLAND PROBLEM

The second major crisis broke out in Poland in the autumn of 1956. 1956 stands out as a year of historical importance in many respects. The 20th Party Congress of the CPSU, held on February 25, 1956, was a turning point. Nikita Khrushchev shocked everyone with his secret speech there. Khrushchev stated that Stalinism was a delusion, denounced the “personality cult” surrounding Stalin, claimed that Stalin was responsible for the deaths and starvation during the “Great Purge”, as well as the Soviet-Yugoslav split, and officially announced that the Stalin era was over.¹⁸ This speech was later leaked to the press and had a great impact in the West as well as in the Eastern Bloc. Following this

speech, COMINTERN was abolished in April 1956, and immediately afterwards Khrushchev and Yugoslav leader Tito came together and began to seek methods for resolving the problems between the two countries. In the same year, Khrushchev stated that trade with West Germany was very important and put forward the idea of "peaceful coexistence." Accordingly, the war between classes would continue because it was part of dialectical history, and it was almost certain that socialism would ultimately prevail, but now Western countries had to perceive that the USSR and state socialism existed, and that the USSR and its allies had to perceive that Western capitalist states existed and would continue to exist, and therefore ways of living together had to be found, and they had to act accordingly.¹⁹ Therefore, the image Moscow gave to the outside world in 1956 was that of a USSR and the Eastern Bloc that wanted peace, was ready and even eager to trade with the West, had learned to live together, and was far removed from the Stalinist worldview. It should not be surprising that the interpretations of this general outlook by the peoples of Eastern Europe focused on the idea that the Soviets would no longer intervene in Eastern European countries and that, as a result, these countries had more room to operate.⁽³⁾

Following the death of Stalinist Prime Minister Bolesław Bierut, the Polish Workers' Party elected Władysław Gomułka, a moderate, liberal socialist who had been imprisoned during Stalin's era on charges of being right-wing and reactionary, to lead the party and thus the country, taking into account the balance within the party. In fact, this event can be seen as a result of the uprising that began in Poznan in June 1956. Workers from Poznan began their actions to protest the shortage of food and consumer goods, poor quality workers' housing, the decline in real incomes and the general deterioration of the economy. While the party initially ignored the uprising, when it realized that it had stirred up public sentiment and gained support from the people, it announced a 50% increase in workers' wages and Gomułka was appointed General Secretary of the Party. However, Gomułka wanted to make reforms and stated that for this to happen he had to actually hold power and demanded the expulsion from the Polish Politburo of Soviet Marshal Konstantin Rokossovsky, the commander of the soldiers who had used force against the workers in Poznań. On 19 October 1956, Gomułka was declared General Secretary of the Party.

On the other hand, Khrushchev was alarmed by these developments, and while the Soviets were conducting military exercises near the Polish border, a group of the highest-ranking Soviet leaders, led by Khrushchev and including Mikoyan, Bulganin and Molotov, flew to Warsaw to demand an accounting from the Polish administration. As a result, Gomułka declared that the Polish army would resist if Soviet troops launched an invasion, but he was also forced to explain that his reforms were definitely not aimed at Poland's secession from the Eastern Bloc. Gomułka's new position was approved by the Soviet leaders, and Gomułka was forced to make a farewell speech stating that the friendship between the Soviet Union and Poland could never be broken, and that Poland and the

Polish people would always live in harmony with the Soviets.

But what Gomułka tried to do was to ignite a glimmer of hope, even more so than it was welcomed in Poland, not only for Poland but also for dissidents in another Eastern European country: Hungary, which would present the USSR with its biggest problem in Eastern Europe.

1956 HUNGARIAN REVOLUTION

While Poland was struggling with Gomułka's rise to power, the Americans' Radio Free Europe was the organization that exaggerated what was happening in Poland and broadcast it to Eastern Europe as a struggle for freedom. Hungarians, listening to the news about Gomułka and Poland, began to believe that their own country's problems could be solved with a similar change of government.

The Hungarian Workers' Party was led by Matyas Rakósi from its founding in 1947. Rakósi described himself as a "devout Stalinist" and "Stalin's greatest [Hungarian] disciple". Therefore, it can be said that he was not well regarded by the Hungarian people or the Soviet government that came to power after Stalin's death. Rakósi was forced to give up the premiership to Imre Nagy for two years in 1953,²¹ but continued as Party General Secretary until the summer of 1956. Nagy was dismissed from office in 1955 on the grounds that he had engaged in practices that were detrimental to the Party and spent some time in prison.

Rakósi, in an attempt to use the June 1956 Poznań events to his advantage, had prepared a list of 400 "enemies of the regime" and had requested their immediate execution by firing squad. However, he was unable to do so because he was removed from office on July 13 when Soviet Politburo member Anastas Mikoyan arrived in Budapest in a surprise raid, in line with one of the items Tito had put forward in his bargaining with the Soviets: "the most vicious enemies of Tito." Rakósi's removal from office was officially announced on July 19. Rakósi was very ill and could only continue his life by receiving treatment in Moscow. The Hungarian leader would remain in the Kyrgyz Federative Socialist Republic of the USSR until his death in 1971. After Rakósi's transfer to the USSR, Ernst Gerö became Party General Secretary and the next leader, János Kádár, became Central Committee Secretary. Gerö had promised a "white slate" policy, but the changes made within the Hungarian Workers' Party and its extension, the bureaucracy, were made reluctantly.²² This change fell far short of the wishes and expectations of the Hungarian people.

On October 15-16, 1956, four days before Gomułka was declared Party leader in Poland, students gathered in Szeged, one of the university towns of Hungary, to demand the re-establishment of the Independent Hungarian University Students' Union MEFESz, thus forming a new opposition group independent of the Party. This student movement was very important for three main reasons: a) they created a brand new, democratic opposition platform that contradicted the Party's understanding; b) they had clear and unambiguous demands for democracy, national sovereignty in their own homeland, land reform; c) student spokespeople explained their demands and plans for solutions to

other schools, factories, and local and national bureaucrats, and began to prepare for general action. The meeting at the Technical University of Budapest on October 22, 1956 was like a preliminary to a revolution. While this was happening, Hungarian leaders, including Ernő Gerő, Prime Minister Hegedüs and Kádár, were on a trip to Yugoslavia to gain Tito's support and only returned on the morning of 23 October.

The demonstration, which began at 14:30 on October 23, 1956, turned from a silent march showing solidarity with Poland into a national uprising during the day. The Soviets began to be called to leave Hungary and the resignation of the government. Imre Nagy, who addressed the group after a group of 200,000 people gathered in front of the Hungarian Parliament called him, became the new leader of Hungary as a result of a people's revolution on the night of October 23 and began his new duty on the morning of October 24. The revolutionaries wanted the "occupying" Soviet army to leave the country, an end to military, political and economic dependency, a review of treaties that were detrimental to the country and the use of national symbols instead of Soviet-style symbols. Soviet troops reached Budapest on the morning of October 24 but did not receive a direct attack order until October 28. On the night of October 27-28, Nagy proposed and made the Politburo accept a compromise and solidarity and agreement with the rebels. On the other hand, by October 29, many politicians from both the Gomulka and Tito administrations had visited Hungary and expressed their support for Nagy and his supporters. Soviet troops returned to their barracks on October 30.

However, the situation changed immediately after this, when the Soviets decided that the revolution could no longer be stopped and that they had to take action. After Nagy announced Hungary's withdrawal from the Warsaw Pact and its neutrality, Tito and Gomulka left Nagy alone

They left,²³ the Americans and Westerners in general never sent the aid they had promised to Hungary, and on October 31 Soviet troops launched a counter-offensive aimed at crushing the revolution. On November 1, an alternative government was formed by the Soviets under the leadership of János Kádár. On November 4, 1956, Budapest was captured by the Soviets; Kádár became the country's new leader, and the Hungarian Revolution of 1956 was suppressed. During the Hungarian Revolution, 25,000 people died, more than 150,000 Hungarians fled their country to the West,²⁴ and many who remained were tried by the Kádár administration. Prime Minister Imre Nagy was captured, tried and executed on June 16, 1958.⁽⁴⁾

The Hungarian Revolution marked the beginning of Khrushchev's policy of hardening against the West. At the same time, the people of the Eastern Bloc countries saw that they should not expect help from the West, that their fate was in their own hands and the Soviets'. The fiasco of the British and French occupation of Suez due to the problems in the Suez Canal, which coincided with the Hungarian Revolution, was cited as the reason for the US not to intervene during the Cold War, but the truth was that the US had no chance of taking any action that would provoke the USSR; the Westerners also believed in Khrushchev's idea of

"peaceful coexistence." However, this was far from the end of the problems between the two sides.

Indeed, under Khrushchev, the Western and Eastern Blocks would come closest to the point of the world's total annihilation with the Cuban Missile Crisis. A change of leader did not mean the end of the rivalry between the US and the USSR, between the Western and Eastern Blocks. The overthrow of Khrushchev in a palace coup in 1964 and the replacement of Leonid Brezhnev did not, by itself, necessitate a change of approach. During a significant part of the Brezhnev period, until the end of 1979, instead of tension and conflict, both blocks accepted the idea of a softening and continuing their coexistence, the opening of European countries, especially West Germany, to Eastern Europe, the beginning of the Turkish-Soviet rapprochement and the establishment of many important heavy industry facilities in Türkiye by the USSR, all of these developments were not due to a change of leader, but to the conditions of global politics and the economy creating obligations for both blocks. Détente/Détente is not ultimately about the transfer of leadership from Stalin to Khrushchev or from Khrushchev to Brezhnev, but is the result of the indirect influence of world economic and political conditions on both sides. However, with such an approach, Stalin's effects on his own country and Eastern Europe should not be reduced to the conditions of the time.

CONCLUSION

In the last period of World War II, the leaders of the USA and the USSR, while constructing their post-war worlds, created very different sets of ideas and convinced themselves that the new order would be most beneficial for them. The USA's proposals that shaped the international system continued to be brought to the agenda by Truman after Roosevelt's death and the foundations of today's economic and diplomatic structure were laid, while Stalin's ideas brought Eastern Europe to a socialist order and thus led to the formation of the concept of the Cold War. The Cold War took shape with the emergence of the German Question and its acuteness, and as a result, Eastern Europe turned into a geography consisting of countries with officially Socialist regimes and governed under Soviet control.

The order that Stalin had in mind included countries governed by more than one Socialist regime and solidarity between them. The order that the Soviets established in Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, Czechoslovakia, Poland and the German Democratic Republic, on the one hand, gave the Soviet government the opportunity to implement Socialism in different environments, and on the other hand, by creating a "buffer zone" between the USSR and Western Europe, it made it easier for the Soviet government to defend against conventional war. Regardless of whether each of these countries wanted a socialist regime, and even against the wishes of the people in general, a new era was born with the construction of Socialism, and Stalin's policies, sometimes brutal, also played a role in this.

When we look at European history from the end of World War II until the period when Khrushchev consolidated his power, we see that, as mentioned above, different approaches were effective for the Western al-

lies and the USSR, and that the focus of the Soviet system turned into the construction of socialism in many countries, also due to the devastation of the war, and that the establishment of satellite regimes in the territories recaptured from the German Third Reich was at the top of the list of importance.

For the Soviet administration, these satellite regimes not only provided a “buffer zone” that would prevent their own territories from being directly attacked, but also offered the opportunity to experiment on the possibility of individuals who had internalized and adopted *Homo Sovieticus*, that is, Soviet-style socialism, actually growing up outside the USSR. However, it soon became apparent that such new motivation would not be easy in these newly Socialist countries. Even in the Berlin Crisis, which can be called the first important event of the Cold War, it had become clear that East Germany and East Berlin would not voluntarily choose Soviet-style Socialism without Soviet military pressure. Later, from Stalin’s death until Khrushchev took over, events in the German Democratic Republic, Poland, and especially Hungary showed that the kind of social transformation the Soviets desired would not take place.

On the other hand, the Western Bloc, led by the US, was also focused on restoring Western Europe to its pre-war state during this period, and either they were indifferent to what was happening in Eastern Europe, or the leading Western powers, the US, Britain and France, promised to help with anti-USSR demonstrations and uprisings in the region, but this help never arrived. During the Hungarian Revolution of 1956, the US repeated the promise of military aid to the Hungarian people on “Radio Free Europe”, which led to an increase in the number of deaths and injuries in Hungary, while at the same time it had the effect of eliminating the positive, almost idealistic way of thinking about the US and the West in Eastern Europe. The people of the countries in Eastern Europe that were liberated from the Nazis by the Soviets and turned into satellite regimes saw by the end of 1956 that neither the Soviet nor the American governments would help them. The struggle that would follow would begin to develop within the framework of the more relaxed conditions of the *Détente/Détente* period that began with Brezhnev replacing Khrushchev in 1964, with the organization of national opposition in countries, efforts to make the voice of the opposition heard through prohibited handprints

(*samizdat*) by the regime, and with organizations in universities. Consequently, the methods that existed from the end of World War II until the mid-1950s would differ in the following period, and the national independence struggle of the Eastern European countries would be continued with different methods. The Eastern European opposition movements that would become even stronger in the late 1980s would eventually pioneer the integration of the Eastern European countries into the liberal democratic system after they broke away from Soviet influence, also under the influence of Gorbachev’s policies.

References

1. EDMONDS, Robin, “Churchill and Stalin”, Robert Blake-William Roger Louis, ed., Churchill, Oxford University Press, Oxford 2003.
2. EROL, Mehmet Seyfettin, “The Balkans in the Cold War Period”, Osman Karatay-Bilgehan A. Gökdağ, eds., *Balkans Handbook*, Volume 1, Karam and Vadi Publications, Ankara 2006, pp. 647-662.
3. EROL, Mehmet Seyfettin-Emre Ozan, “Ideology and Foreign Policy”, Ertan Efeğil and Mehmet Seyfettin Erol, eds., *Theoretical Approaches in Foreign Policy Analysis: The Example of Turkish Foreign Policy*, Barış Kitap, Ankara, 2012, pp. 347-375.
4. KARADELİ, Cem, “Soviets and Crises in Eastern Europe during the Stalin and Khrushchev Periods”, *Ufuk University Social Sciences Institute Journal*, 8(15), 2019, pp. 239-253.
5. LÍTVÁN, György, *The Hungarian Revolution of 1956: Reform, Revolt, and Repression*, Longman, London 1996.
6. MCCAULEY, Martin, *Russia, America, & the Cold War: 1949-1991*, Longman, London 1998.
7. PARTOS, Gabriel, *The World That Came In From The Cold: Perspectives From East and West On the Cold War*, BBC/Royal Institute of International Affairs, London 2013.
8. PEACOCK, Herbert Leonard, *A History of Modern Europe: 1789-1981*, Heinemann Educational, Oxford 2012.
9. WEEKS, Theodore S., *Across the Revolutionary Divide: Russia and the USSR, 1861-1945*, Wiley-Blackwell, Malden, MA 2011.
10. WILLIAMSON, David *Europe and the Cold War: 1945-91*, Hodder & Stoughton, London 2001.